

Multiplier Effects in the Input-Output Model with Two Exogenous Sectors

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Abstract

The study extends the input-output (IO) model to the more realistic situation in which the economy is not only driven by agricultural productive shocks but also by fiscal policies on the import exchange rate. The multiplier effect of both the agricultural shocks and fiscal stimulus on industrial output are computed from the Make and Use Tables of the Argentina's System of National Accounts (SNA) for 103 industries and compared with elasticities obtained through other econometric methods. Along the paper, guidelines are given for the computation of the empirical direct requirement matrices (needed in the aforementioned models) from the Make and Use Tables of the SNA.

Key Words: Input-Output model, fiscal multipliers, agriculture, Make and Use Tables, System of National Accounts, Argentina

1. Leontief's Input-Output Model Overview

Given the Make (\mathbf{S}), Use or Intermediate Demand (\mathbf{D}_I) and Final Demand (\mathbf{D}_F) from the Make and Use Tables (MUT) from the National Accounts System, the accounting identity $\mathbf{S}\mathbf{1}_k = \mathbf{D}_I\mathbf{1}_k + \mathbf{D}_F\mathbf{1}_q$ may be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{S}'(\mathbf{T}_n^{-1}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{1}_k) &= (\mathbf{S}'\mathbf{T}_n^{-1}\mathbf{D}_I\mathbf{T}_k^{-1})\mathbf{S}'\mathbf{1}_n + (\mathbf{S}'\mathbf{T}_n^{-1})\mathbf{D}_F\mathbf{1}_q \\ \mathbf{x} &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + (\mathbf{S}'\mathbf{T}_n^{-1})\mathbf{d}_F, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{A} is a technological matrix and \mathbf{x} is the industrial output. Since the supply of produced goods must equal the demand of produced and non-produced factors, it may be stated that $\mathbf{p}'(\mathbf{S}'\mathbf{T}_n^{-1})\mathbf{d}_F = \boldsymbol{\pi}'\mathbf{y}$, where $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ is a price vector of non-produced factors and $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{B}_k\mathbf{x}$ is a quantity vector of non-produced factors. Then, equation (1) turns into a price model

$$\mathbf{p}' = \mathbf{p}'\mathbf{A} + \boldsymbol{\pi}'\mathbf{B}_k. \quad (2)$$

So, the full IO model is given by the set of equations

$$\max_{\mathbf{x} \geq \mathbf{0}} \{\mathbf{p}'(\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A})\mathbf{x}\} \quad s.t. \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A})^{-1}(\mathbf{S}'\mathbf{T}_n^{-1})\mathbf{d}_F \\ \mathbf{p} = (\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A}')^{-1}\mathbf{B}'_k\boldsymbol{\pi} \\ \mathbf{p}'\mathbf{x} \leq \text{const.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

More details regarding model (3) can be found in the texts of ten Raa (2005) and Miller & Blair (2009). It's important to note that output is completely endogenous in (3). However, the output of some sectors are not driven by final demand, but rather by supply exogenous shocks. So, a better representation of an economy with such a feature is given by the next proposition.

Proposition 1. The IO model with one exogenous sector

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{x}_1 = (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}(\mathbf{S}'_1\mathbf{T}_n^{-1}\mathbf{d}_1^F) + (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}\mathbf{a}_{12}x_2 \\ \mathbf{p}_1 = (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1}(\mathbf{B}'_{11}\boldsymbol{\pi}_1 + \mathbf{b}_{21}\boldsymbol{\pi}_2) + (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1}\mathbf{a}_{21}p_2 \\ \mathbf{p}'_1\mathbf{x}_1 \leq \text{const.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Proof. The proof can be found in (Frank, 2023a). \square

This decomposition is useful to simulate the output or price pass-through from one sector to the others. For example, the pass-through of (i) harvest failures due to droughts and floods (x_2 is agricultural output), (ii) real estate and infrastructure plans (x_2 is construction output), even (iii) the pass-through tariffs on imports ($p_2 = p_M\theta$, where θ is the tariff or exchange rate gap) and $\mathbf{a}_{12} = \mathbf{b}_{21} = \mathbf{0}_r$.

In general, $(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}\mathbf{a}_{ij}$ is the pass-through vector associated to an arbitrary x_j sector, while $\boldsymbol{\lambda}'_1 = \mathbf{1}'_r(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}$ is the demand-multipliers vector in which each element represents the increase in total output due to a unit increase in the demand of the corresponding sector.

2. Pass-through Factors, Multipliers & Elasticities

The computing formulas of pass-through factors, multipliers and elasticities that arise from (4) are not obvious and need to be clarified, as well as their interrelationships.

Proposition 2. In (4) the exact exogenous demand and supply multipliers are, respectively,

$$\begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\lambda}'_1 = \left(\mathbf{1}'_r + \frac{\mathbf{a}'_{21}}{1 - a_{22}} \right) \left[(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11}) - \frac{\mathbf{a}_{12}\mathbf{a}'_{21}}{1 - a_{22}} \right]^{-1} \\ \lambda_2 = \frac{1 + \mathbf{1}'_r(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}\mathbf{a}_{12}}{1 - a_{22} - \mathbf{a}'_{21}(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}\mathbf{a}_{12}} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Proof. The inverse of Leontief's block partitioned matrix (Tzon-Tzer Lu & Sheng-Hua Shiou 2002) is

$$(\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A})^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}^{-1} & -(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}(-\mathbf{A}_{12})\mathbf{B}^{-1} \\ -(\mathbf{I}_s - \mathbf{A}_{22})^{-1}(-\mathbf{A}_{21})\mathbf{C}^{-1} & \mathbf{B}^{-1} \end{bmatrix},$$

where

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{C} = (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11}) - (-\mathbf{A}_{12})(\mathbf{I}_s - \mathbf{A}_{22})^{-1}(-\mathbf{A}_{21}) \\ \mathbf{B} = (\mathbf{I}_s - \mathbf{A}_{22}) - (-\mathbf{A}_{21})(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}(-\mathbf{A}_{12}). \end{cases}$$

Particularly, if $s = 1$ and $r = k - 1$, the vector of multipliers of all sectors except the last one is

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda}'_r = \mathbf{1}'_r\mathbf{C}^{-1} + \frac{\mathbf{a}'_{21}\mathbf{C}^{-1}}{1 - a_{22}} = \left(\mathbf{1}'_r + \frac{\mathbf{a}'_{21}}{1 - a_{22}} \right) \left[(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11}) - \frac{\mathbf{a}_{12}\mathbf{a}'_{21}}{1 - a_{22}} \right]^{-1},$$

while the multiplier of the last sector is

$$\lambda_k = \mathbf{1}'_r(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}\mathbf{a}_{12}b^{-1} + b^{-1} = \frac{1 + \mathbf{1}'_r(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}\mathbf{a}_{12}}{1 - a_{22} - \mathbf{a}'_{21}(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}\mathbf{a}_{12}}.$$

\square

In practice, $\mathbf{a}_{12}\mathbf{a}'_{21}$ and $\mathbf{a}'_{21}(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}\mathbf{a}_{12}$ are negligible and can be omitted from the formulas. In the tariff-on-imports version of model (4), $a_{22} = 0$ and $\mathbf{a}_{12} = \mathbf{0}_r$ (as well as $\mathbf{b}_{21} = \mathbf{0}_r$) so $\boldsymbol{\lambda}'_1 \approx (\mathbf{1}'_r + \mathbf{a}'_{21})(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}$ and $\lambda_2 = 1$.

Proposition 3. In (4) the demand and the (exogenous) output elasticities at a certain base period are, respectively,

$$\begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\Gamma}_{r \times r} = \mathbf{T}_r^{*-1}(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1} \text{diag}(\mathbf{S}'_1 \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{d}_1^{\text{F}*}) \\ \gamma = \mathbf{T}_r^{*-1}(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}\mathbf{a}_{12}x_2^*, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where the asterisk means that the variable is evaluated at the base period.

Proof. Let's recall first that the derivatives of the (endogenous) supply with respect to the final demand and the exogenous supply are, respectively,

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_1}{\partial \mathbf{d}_1^{\text{F}*}} = (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} \quad \text{y} \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_1}{\partial x_2} = (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{a}_{12}.$$

Then, rewriting the IO quantity model and pre-multiplying both sides by \mathbf{T}_r^{-1} , and introducing the product of $\mathbf{D}_1 = \text{diag}(\mathbf{S}'_1 \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{d}_1^{\text{F}*})$ by its own inverse,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{T}_r^{-1} \mathbf{x}_1 &= [\mathbf{T}_r^{-1} (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{D}_1] (\mathbf{D}_1^{-1} \mathbf{d}_1^{\text{F}*}) + x_2^* \mathbf{T}_r^{-1} (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{a}_{12} \begin{pmatrix} x_2 \\ x_2^* \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \left[\mathbf{T}_r^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}'_1}{\partial \mathbf{d}_1^{\text{F}*}} \mathbf{D}_1 \right] (\mathbf{D}_1^{-1} \mathbf{d}_1^{\text{F}*}) + \left(\mathbf{T}_r^{-1} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_1}{\partial x_2} x_2^* \right) \begin{pmatrix} x_2 \\ x_2^* \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

which is the one-exogenous-sector model scaled to unity at the base period. The matrices that pre-multiply $\mathbf{D}_1^{-1} \mathbf{d}_1^{\text{F}*}$ and x_2/x_2^* are elasticity-matrices at that base year, while the sum of the elements of each column is the overall multiplicative effect of a 1% increase in the demand of the corresponding sector, or in the supply of the exogenous sector. That is,

$$\mathbf{1}'_r \boldsymbol{\gamma}_j = \sum_{i=1}^r \frac{\partial x_{1i}}{\partial d_{1j}^{\text{F}*}} \frac{d_{1j}^{\text{F}*}}{x_{1i}}$$

□

Note that $\mathbf{I}_{r \times r}$ and $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ represent the “parameters” of (4) when \mathbf{d}_1^{F} and x_2 are scaled to unity at a certain base period. So, pass-through factors and elasticities are equivalent metrics when \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{d}_1^{F} and x_2 are evaluated at the same period, as well as multipliers are equivalent to the aggregated elasticities.

3. The IO Model with Two Exogenous Sectors

A more complex situation arises when two sectors are exogenous as in the argentinean economy, where both agriculture and imports are subject to shocks. An extension of proposition 1 to such a circumstance is given by proposition 4.

Proposition 4. The IO model with two exogenous sectors

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{x}_1 = (\mathbf{I}_{r-1} - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1} (\mathbf{S}'_1 \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{d}_1^{\text{F}}) + (\mathbf{I}_{r-1} - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{a}_{12} x_2 \\ \mathbf{p}_1 = (\mathbf{I}_{r-1} - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} (\mathbf{B}'_{11} \boldsymbol{\pi}_1 + \mathbf{b}_{21} \pi_2) + (\mathbf{I}_{r-1} - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{a}_{21} p_2 + \\ \quad + (\mathbf{I}_{r-1} - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} \left[\mathbf{a}_{31} + \frac{\mathbf{a}'_{12} (\mathbf{I}_{r-1} - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{a}_{31} - a_{32}}{(1 - a_{22}) - \mathbf{a}'_{12} (\mathbf{I}_{r-1} - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{a}_{21}} \mathbf{a}_{21} \right] p_3 \\ \mathbf{x}'_1 \mathbf{p}_1 \leq \text{const.} \end{array} \right. \quad (7)$$

where x_2 means agricultural output and p_3 import prices. These last ones can in turn be decomposed as $p_M \theta$, where p_M is a vector of international prices and θ the exchange rate including tariffs.

Proof. Let's call

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_{11} & \mathbf{c}_{12} \\ \mathbf{c}'_{21} & c_{22} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{11} & \mathbf{a}_{12} & \mathbf{a}_{13} \\ \mathbf{a}'_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ \mathbf{a}'_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{where} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a}_{13} \\ a_{23} \\ a_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0}_k$$

in the agricultural and tariffs driven model. By proposition 1, we write

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{x}_1 = (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{C}_{11})^{-1} (\mathbf{S}'_1 \mathbf{T}_n^{-1} \mathbf{d}_1^{\text{F}}) \\ \mathbf{p}_1 = (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{C}'_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{B}'_{11} \boldsymbol{\pi}_N + (\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{C}'_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{c}_{21} p_3 \\ \mathbf{x}'_1 \mathbf{p}_1 \leq \text{const.} \end{array} \right. \quad (8)$$

Then, after solving $(\mathbf{I}_r - \mathbf{C}_{11})^{-1}$ in the same fashion as $(\mathbf{I}_k - \mathbf{A}_{11})^{-1}$ in proposition 2, and collecting terms we get (7). □

Note that the demand and agricultural multipliers are identical to those of (4), while the multiplier of the imports prices is

$$\lambda_{p_3} \approx \mathbf{1}'_{r-1} (\mathbf{I}_{r-1} - \mathbf{A}'_{11})^{-1} \mathbf{a}_{31} + \frac{a_{32}}{1 - a_{22}} \quad (9)$$

4. Computing Agriculture and Tariff Multipliers from Argentina’s 2018 MUT

Table 1 summarizes the computation of 103 pass-through factors for agricultural production and import tariffs. The complete computation is available through the author upon request. The multiplier effect of each exogenous variable (computed as a weighted average of the pass-through factors) is recorded at the end of the table. These last can also be interpreted as the 2018 elasticities of agricultural production and tariffs on imports. Both elasticities are in line with 0.02 and 0.12, respectively, computed by Frank (2023b, 2023c) through an error correction model (ECM) and vector autoregression (VAR). But, unlike these models, decomposition (7) allows the computation of elasticities of the 104 MUT activities (see INDEC, 2021), which would be almost impossible to compute by ECM or VAR due to the unavailability of time series that long.

Table 1: Pass-through of agricultural output and import tariffs on 11 sectors out of 103, and the overall multiplier effects for the Argentinean economy.

Selected isic rev.3.1 activities	Agriculture	Tariffs
111 Extraction of crude oil and natural gas	0,0272	0,1070
1541 Manufacture of bakery products	0,0007	0,1516
210 Manufacture of paper and paper products	0,0025	0,2487
271 Basic iron and steel industries	0,0045	0,2927
291 Manufacture of general purpose machinery	0,0024	0,3052
341/2 Manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers, etc.	0,0126	0,3752
450 Construction	0,0027	0,1958
51 Wholesale trade	0,0098	0,2947
52 exc. 526 Retail trade	0,0050	0,1810
602 Truck transportation service	0,0717	0,2148
750 Government, defense and social security	0,0015	0,0672
Aggregate 2018 multipliers/elasticities	0,0703	0,1388

It is worth noting that the MUT published by the National Accounts Office are not as neat as those required for the preceding calculation. For example, wholesale and retail margins, as well as transport margins, are presented away from the Supply and Use Tables, which are valued at basic prices and producer prices, respectively. Broadly speaking, it is recommended to, in first instance, add up the distribution margins and then distribute this aggregate between domestic and imported products according to their share in the total supply; and the, in a second instance, to distribute the margins of domestic products according to the sectorial share of each product. Our experience suggests that this way of margin allocation is the least disruptive to the original supply structure.

5. Conclusion

The paper extends the input-output (IO) model to an economy driven by two exogenous sectors, i.e. agriculture and governmental policies on import tariffs, and clarifies the meaning and computation of pass-through factors, multipliers and elasticities in this new context. The formulas associated to the new model are then used to compute pass-through factors and multiplier effects of agricultural and exchange rate/tariff shocks on the output of 11 out of 103 industries from the MUT of the Argentina’s System of National Accounts. The comparison of these elasticities with those obtained through other econometric methods

yield promising results.

All components of the IO model with exogenous sectors were assumed to be deterministic. While this assumption might seem reasonable for modeling exchange rate shocks, clearly it is not for modeling agricultural output shocks and even prices. The next step in the research will address this point in order to elucidate the statistical properties of \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{p}_1 , and that of the pass-through factors, multipliers and elasticities. In this regard, technical coefficients are expected to acquire new meaning, as they will undoubtedly define the parameters of sectoral output and price distributions.

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